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MONITORING OF DETERMINATION FEATURES OF GASTRONOMIC EVENTS EFFICIENCY

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Topicality. Today, gastronomic tourism in the Black Sea region is under development. a large number of scientists are engaged in the gastronomic culinary development activities and the study of their economic efficiency and promotion in Internet communications, but its impact on the quality of events is insufficiently studied. Therefore, conducting analytical research on the announcement and post-event publications in the information Internet resources of gastronomic events becomes an urgent task. **Purpose and methods.** The aim of the article is to study aspects of the development of the potential of gastronomic tourism in the region, to analyze the impact of advertising announcing the event on various Internet networks on the qualitative and quantitative indicators of event content. The methodological and informational basis of the work are scientific and theoretical works of scientists on the gastronomic tourism development, data obtained during the advertising campaign in open culinary competitions in Mykolayiv, and other culinary events organized and conducted by members of the Association of Culinary Arts of Ukraine. Various general scientific and special research methods are used. **Results.** in order to analyze the advertising promotion effectiveness of gastronomic events through television channels, informational online publications, social networks, tracking the dynamics of incoming traffic. Analysis of awareness in the region about the event indicates that in today's conditions the use of online media has a positive effect. **Conclusions and discussions.** Significantly different rates of targeted advertising on Instagram and Facebook, used by us to promote events only in 2019, the quantitative indicators of coverage in these channels exceed the average views in online media by almost 1000 %. Studies of the data obtained after the events suggest that their conduct increases the number of visitors many times, and sometimes this number reaches 250–300 %. This confirms the economic feasibility of the events holding.

Keywords: gastronomic event, culinary competitions, promotion, targeting, efficiency, advertising.

The topicality of the problem

Formulation of the problem. To date, the number of gastronomic events in the Black Sea region is gradually increasing (M. M. Ohienko & A. V. Ohienko, 2019). The region has a rich historical, cultural, natural, creative potential for the development of this type of tourism. Natural and geographical location, traditions, folklore are the basis for the festivals development that will develop Ukrainian culture and demonstrate the color of the nation. In general, there are various festivals, events, holidays, exhibitions, etc., both in the region and in the territory of the united territorial communities. The main task facing the organizers and local governments is to create conditions for reaching the international level, which will ensure the filling of participants and guests.

The state of the problem study. The following scientists deal with the gastronomic events development and the study of economic efficiency of their implementation and promotion in Internet communications: O.V. Babkin, D.I. Basyuk, O.O. Beidyk, V. Yu. Kotsyubynsky, B.O. Korinny, O.V. Muzychenko-Kozlovskaya, M.I. Peresichny, S.E. Salamatina, S.O. Solntsev, O.A. Stelmakh, K. Yu. Kovalenko, N.V. Yudina, O.V. Shikina (Muzychenko-Kozlovskaya 2012; Lagodiienko et al, 2019; "Stratehichne planuvannia", 2019; "Return on event", 2019).

However, the impact of the effectiveness of promotion in various Internet networks on the quality of events is insufficiently studied. Therefore, conducting analytical studies of announcements and post-event publications in the information Internet resources of gastronomic events becomes an urgent task.

Unresolved issues. There is research of the various types' influence of advertising on the filling of the event by participants and viewers. There is generalization of the economic efficiency of the event by determining the number of visitors and coverage of views of publications.

Purpose and research methods

The purpose of the article is to study the development aspects of the potential of gastronomic events in the region, analysis of the impact of advertising announcing the event on various Internet networks on the events quality, identifying prospects and ways to develop regional gastronomic events. *The methodological and informational bases of the work* are scientific and theoretical works of scientists on the gastronomic events development, data obtained during the advertising campaign in the open culinary competitions «Best Chef 2018» and «Staff Battle 2019» in Mykolayiv. The realization of the defined purpose is based on a systematic approach to the researched problems and various general scientific and special research methods are used.

Research results

The gastronomic potential of Mykolayivshchina is formed by many components, but at creation of image of region it is necessary to pay attention to the organization of gastronomic actions. Gastronomic festivals and competitions have the potential for the development of such events in Mykolayivregion. Currently, this type of activity, given the centuries-old history and preservation of the traditions of the Ukrainian people, is quite young and promising in the regions of Ukraine (M. M. Ohienko

& A. V. Ohienko, 2019). Some festivals and holidays are still spontaneous, which prevents the influx of participants and spectators. Therefore, it is necessary to pay attention to the development of HORECA infrastructure around the event, as this is one of the key factors influencing the decision to participate. Note at one of the events – «Rest actively», which is held in the area of the rock massif, on the banks of the Southern Bug in Yuzhnoukrainsk (the festival is held in the national park «Bug Guard») and has a low occupancy due to lack of infrastructure within locations.

According to the goals of gastronomic events are divided into:

- directly profit-oriented, conducted for commercial purposes by individuals or groups. Profit is generated by participating in the event or as a result of actions in the process (sales, contracts). The purpose of such events is to attract the attention of a large number of participants and encourage them to be active;
- indirectly profit-oriented, carried out by individuals or groups in solving their own problems. The purpose of such events is to create a positive impression and support the implementation of other priorities. Such events may be of a commercial or ideological nature.

Thus, gastronomic events are bright and unusual events aimed at promoting the brand of the region, overcoming seasonal fluctuations, increasing the influx of participants and guests to the region, attracting and developing related industries through memory and extraordinary events and perceptions (Muzychenko-Kozlovska, 2012). Their holding in the regions and in separate territories will strengthen the image of the region as a whole; to convey to a wide range of people its values, features and culture; launch the previous and next information «wave» in the media; develop market demand and increase the number of their participants.

The following features are characteristic of gastronomic events (Lagodiienko et al, 2019):

- the result of the effort is the event itself, and it can neither be postponed nor corrected (“passed as passed”);
- The result is unique, success depends on the subjective perception of visitors;
- the result depends on the number of participants in the event, it is completely depreciated if there are not enough participants (the event is viable due to the fact that it is attended);
- compared to the event result, its preparation is larger than the cost and time and money.

When organizing gastronomic events, the important issue of inviting participants, speakers, presenters, juries, who should be authoritative experts in their field, should be taken into account. Such people themselves are «a brand», the audience perceives their names as a brand. Accordingly, they will be the «face» of the event, which will raise the status and automatically attract the target audience. For example, during gastronomic festivals in Mykolayiv, special guests from abroad, participants of Ukrainian culinary projects and talk shows, members of the international class jury, world champions in culinary arts, well-known chefs in Ukraine were invited.

Sponsorships and partnerships, companies or brands with a similar target audience are often used to organize competitions and to optimize costs, expand coverage, and implement complex projects. In the case of gastronomic events involved producers of agricultural and food products, companies for the production of equipment and facilities for HORECA and others. The partners’ participation in the organization of the

event opens channels for «live» communication of the brand with consumers and provides new vectors of development.

An important indicator of the event is its effectiveness, in planning which it is possible to use data obtained earlier. Different methods are used for calculations, taking into account the following data ("Stratehichne planuvannia", 2019):

- initiating the project, involving participants, sponsors, the public and spectators, motivating them. Creating a press release for the event, promotion through the media, partners, local government;
- to provide comprehensive awareness of the event. Analysis of the effectiveness of advertising channels (television, online information publications, and social networks). It is necessary to monitor the dynamics of incoming traffic on social networks, media coverage, statistics on leads and customers involved in the event, to monitor publications after the event in the media;
- total number of participants in the event. The primary audience is evaluated – the actual participants of the event, those who are present in person, and the secondary audience – are those who are not present at the event in person, but the event still concerns them. Thus, the event partner can publish about him in the media, so he conveys information to his target audience, so the secondary audience is several times larger than the primary and is very important;
- number of participants in different segments and categories. This is a tracking of the participant's behavior during the event, such as movements inside, the length of time spent in different locations. This is easy to do if it is a specialized event, where there are cameras to count the audience or specialized devices, and more difficult – at mass events;
- participants' satisfaction. When assessing the success of the event should take into account the emotional reactions of those present. However, it is absolutely impossible to be completely limited to the reaction of "liked" or "disliked";
- financial indicators. Direct effect from the receipt and sale of products timed to the event, especially from the sale of tickets, goods. ROI (Return on investment) is widely used for commercial gastronomic projects ("Rentabelnist investytsii", 2019). This is an evaluation criterion for the return on investment in the event. The total costs of organizing and conducting the event are recorded in the estimate. Profits can be measured by calculating sales or other targeted actions after the event. For non-profit ROE (Return on event) is used – an indicator of the level of involvement, attitude of guests and impressions of the event ("Return on event", 2019).

After analyzing these data, it is possible to compare gastronomic activities and their success. When planning the next event, you need to use the data obtained. With a high probability we can assume that the next event or part of it will be somewhat similar to the previous one.

During 2017–2020, a number of image gastronomic events (festivals, competitions, contests, etc.) were held in Mykolayiv region in order to increase the city's attractiveness and increase the flow of guests. As part of the festival's gastronomic movement, the annual open all-Ukrainian competitions in culinary art and service «Best Chef 2018» and «Staff Battle 2019» took place. In order to analyze the effectiveness of advertising promotion of gastronomic events through television channels, informational Internet publications, social networks, tracking the dynamics of incoming traffic, media coverage, statistics on ice (M. Ohienko & A. Ohienko, 2020) and involved participants (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Analysis of the effectiveness of advertising channels (number of views of the publication) when announcing the event
 Source: Based on ("V Nikolaeve proidet", 2018; "V Nikolaeve molodye", 2018; "V Nikolaeve proshel", 2018, "Staff Battle", 2019)

Analysis of awareness in the region about the gastronomic event indicates that in today's conditions, the use of Internet media has a positive effect. During the study period, the communication channels used to promote the event showed almost the same number of views. The data on the use of targeted advertising on Instagram and Facebook, which we used to promote the event in 2019, differ significantly; the quantitative indicators of coverage in these channels exceed the average rates of views in on-line media by almost 1000 %. Therefore, when announcing the next event, we propose to direct the main part of the advertising budget to targeting.

Monitoring the publication of the event in the media indicates the delivery of information to the secondary audience, those who could not attend the event in person, but the event still affects them, and shows the effectiveness of information channels. The analysis on the example of the annual open all-Ukrainian competitions in culinary art and service «Best Chef» and «Staff Battle» allows you to effectively use existing channels. In 2018, the results of the event were published on the YouTube channels of local TV companies (Fig. 2).

Thus, on the Internet channel of the public broadcaster TV channel «Mykolaiv» ("Staff Battle", 2019) with 13.1 thousand subscribers, the number of views of the video was 106 or 0.8 % of the total, on the YouTube channel of the TV and radio company «MARCH» [13], the number subscribers of which is 4.7 thousand, views of this event are 117 or 2.5 %, similar figures are observed on the YouTube channel of the TV and radio company «NIS-TV» 35 channel ("Novyi den", 2018), where the number of content views was 36 with a total number of subscribers 2, 93 thousand, i.e. 1.3 % of the total. The results of the study of the views number of video reports of the studied event indicate low traffic to the Internet pages of TV channels.

After analyzing the budget costs of the project of the event «Best Chef» and taking into account the results (number of views), we can say that the above channels to convey information to the secondary audience of gastronomic events are ineffective.

Fig. 2. The number of video content views of the open all-Ukrainian contests on culinary arts and the service “Best Cook”

Source: Based on (“Staff Battle”, 2019; “Novyi den”, 2018; “V Mykolaievi zmahalsia”, 2018; “Nagrazhdenie pobeditelei”, 2018)

In order to convey information to the target audience (HORECA and other interested listeners), the results of the festivals are published on the Internet media. The analysis of publications in the Internet media is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Number of views on internet media publications in Mykolaiv region
 Source: Based on (“V Nikolaeve sostoitsia”, 2019; “V Nikolaeve povara”, 2019a; “V Nikolaeve povara”, 2019b)

The results of monitoring the reviews of publications on gastronomic events in the online media show that during the study period among the readers of the online publication «Crime.NO» ("V Nikolaev povara", 2019a) the number of secondary audience interested in the event almost doubles and is about 10 thousand views, among readers of the online publication «Niklife» ("V Nikolaev povara", 2019b) the number of readers has tripled compared to 2018, the number of views of the publication of online media «Nikolaev 24» has hardly changed. Comparing the average number of views in online publications with views on YouTube of TV channels, which in 2018 averaged 4300 and 150 views, respectively, we can say that the publication of information about gastronomic events on the pages of online media is more effective than television channels, so these studies should be taken into account when planning and organizing advertising campaigns for the following activities.

An important indicator of the gastronomic events effectiveness is the number of participants. The event is considered viable due to the fact that it is attended. During such events there is a difficulty in counting the number of participants and spectators: firstly, most events take place in open areas, and secondly, during the event the number of participants and spectators changes. If we consider gastronomic event resources, there are a number of requirements for their holding, so it is more convenient to organize such events in closed locations, and at the same time simplifies the calculation of the number of participants. The Metro shopping center is often a permanent partner in the organization of gastronomic movement and culinary activities "TC "METRO" № 23", 2019). Competitions on the basis of the Metro shopping center (Fig. 4) take place in many regions of Ukraine, which gives researchers the opportunity to assess the effectiveness of the event in terms of site attendance.

Fig. 4. Number of visitors to the location (Metro Center) for gastronomic events
 Source: Developed by the author on the basis of ("TC "METRO" № 23", 2019)

Studies of data obtained after gastronomic events suggest that the organization of the event increases the number of visitors many times, sometimes reaching 250–300 % compared to the same day of the week without such events, which confirms the economic feasibility of their holding. Studies of data obtained after gastronomic events suggest that the organization of the event increases the number of visitors many times, sometimes reaching 250–300 % compared to the same day of the week without such events, which confirms the economic feasibility of their holding.

Taking into account the above studies of the advertising campaign of events, it can be argued that the results can be used not only for gastronomic tourism events, but also for other events (concert, sports, ethnic, etc.) taking into account the characteristics of each event.

Within the limits of the festival «Mykolayiv. Vintage cuisine «the idea of search and reproduction of the historical menu and recipes of Mykolayivshchina, namely its vintage cuisine is realized. Representatives of the Association of Culinary Arts of Ukraine together with the Department of Education and Science of the Mykolayiv Regional State Administration, as well as representatives of restaurants of Mykolayiv and educational institutions that train students in the specialty «Cook» actively participated in the work on this project.

Representatives of the Mykolayiv branch of Association of cooks of Ukraine together with employees of the State archive of the Mykolayiv area and the Mykolayiv regional universal scientific library searched for menus and ancient recipes of dishes (fig. 5) of the Black Sea region.

Fig. 5. Published menus of restaurants in Mykolaiv at the end of the 19th and early 20th centuries

Source: Compiled by the author according to the State Archives of Mykolaiv Region and Mykolaiv Region Universal Scientific Library

Masters, pupils and students of institutions of higher, vocational education of the specialties «Cook» and «Hotel and restaurant business», and also cooks of restaurants of Mykolayiv and Ukraine were involved for elaboration of dishes by Mykolayivshchina

vintage cuisine. Technological maps and descriptions of recipes of reproduced dishes presented in modern interpretation are obtained.

All dishes were evaluated by the professional jury of the competition and handed over for introduction to the chefs of the best regional restaurants. These restaurants will be included in the «Best gastronomic tour of Mykolayiv», within which guests of the city and locals will be able to taste the reproduced dishes, to get acquainted with local traditions, the restored historical recipes of the city of Mykolayiv and the Black Sea region.

Communicative platforms have been created for representatives of the HORECA industry of Mykolayiv region and Ukraine, higher education institutions and specialized educational institutions that train restaurant specialists, comprehensively promote the development of professional skills of industry workers, intensive exchange of experience, professional training, and chef prestige.

Conclusions and results discussion

After monitoring the specifics of determining the effectiveness of gastronomic events, we conclude that an important factor influencing the effectiveness of the event is to ensure comprehensive awareness of the event, as evidenced by its analysis in the region on the example of gastronomic competitions in culinary arts and service «Best Chef».

During the study period, various communication channels were used to promote the event (social networks Facebook and Instagram, online media, television), resulting in a comparative analysis of the coverage of stakeholders in each of them.

The research found that the quantitative indicators of content views when using targeted advertising on Instagram and Facebook significantly exceed the average rates of views in online media. During the 5-day advertising campaign, the target audience reached more than 22 thousand impressions, despite the fact that the total number of views in the online media is about 5 thousand, in addition, when using targeted advertising filters are selected target audience: age, region, area activities and others that allowed us to convey information online in accordance with the portrait of the target audience.

When assessing the gastronomic activities effectiveness, the main factor is the total number of secondary audience. Comparing the average number of views in online publications with views on YouTube TV channels, we can say that the publication of information about gastronomic events on the Internet media is more effective, so these studies should be considered when planning and organizing advertising campaigns for future events.

An important factor in determining the gastronomic events effectiveness is the number of participants in the primary audience. During the calculations of the number of guests and participants of the studied events, their increase is observed in times, compared to the same day of the week without such events, which confirms the economic feasibility of their holding.

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МОНІТОРИНГ ОСОБЛИВОСТЕЙ ВИЗНАЧЕННЯ ЕФЕКТИВНОСТІ ГАСТРОНОМІЧНИХ ПОДІЄВИХ ЗАХОДІВ

Актуальність. На сьогоднішній день гастрономічний туризм у Причорноморському регіоні перебуває на стадії розвитку. Питаннями розвитку гастрономічних кулінарних заходів і дослідження їх економічної ефективності та просування в інтернет-комунікаціях займається велика кількість науковців, проте його вплив на якісні показники наповнення івентів досліджений недостатньо. Тому проведення аналітичних досліджень анонсування та післязаходових публікацій в інформаційних інтернет-ресурсах гастрономічних заходів стає актуальним завданням. **Мета і методи.** Метою статті є дослідження аспектів розвитку потенціалу гастрономічного туризму регіону, проведення аналізу впливу реклами анонсування заходу в різних інтернет-мережах на якісні та кількісні показники наповнення

івентів. Методологічною й інформаційною основою роботи є наукові та теоретичні праці вчених щодо розвитку гастрономічного туризму, дані, отримані під час проведення рекламної кампанії в рамках відкритих кулінарних конкурсів у м. Миколаїв, та інших кулінарних заходів, організованих і проведених членами Асоціації кулінарів України. Використано різноманітні загальнонаукові та спеціальні методи дослідження. **Результати.** З метою аналізу ефективності рекламного просування гастрономічних заходів через канали телебачення, інформаційні інтернет-видання, соцмережі здійснено відстеження динаміки вхідного трафіку. Аналіз поінформованості в регіоні про проведення подієвого заходу вказує, що в умовах сьогодення використання інтернет-засобів масової інформації має свій позитивний ефект. **Висновки та обговорення.** Суттєво відрізняються показники застосування таргетованої реклами в мережах Instagram та Facebook, використаної нами для просування заходів тільки у 2019 році, кількісні показники охоплення в даних каналах перевищують середні показники переглядів в інтернет-ЗМІ майже на 1000 %. Дослідження даних, отриманих після заходів, дозволяють стверджувати, що їх проведення збільшує кількість відвідувачів у рази, а інколи ця кількість сягає 250–300 %. Це підтверджує економічну доцільність проведення заходів.

Ключові слова: гастрономічний захід, кулінарні конкурси, просування, таргетинг, ефективність, реклама.

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МОНИТОРИНГ ОСОБЕННОСТЕЙ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ГАСТРОНОМИЧЕСКИХ СОБЫТИЙНЫХ МЕРОПРИЯТИЙ

Актуальность. На сегодняшний день количество проведения гастрономических событийных мероприятий в Причерноморском регионе незначительное. Вопросами развития гастрономических кулінарных мероприятий и исследованием их экономической эффективности и продвижения в интернет-коммуникациях занимается множество ученых,

однако влияние эффективности продвижения в различных интернет-сетях на качественные показатели наполнения ивентов исследованы недостаточно. Поэтому проведение аналитических исследований анонсирования и послесобытийных публикаций в информационных интернет-ресурсах гастрономических мероприятий становится актуальной задачей. **Цель и методы.** Целью статьи является исследование аспектов развития потенциала гастрономического туризма региона, проведение анализа влияния рекламы анонсирования мероприятия в различных интернет-сетях на качественные показатели наполнения ивентов. Методологической и информационной основой работы являются научные и теоретические труды ученых по развитию гастрономического туризма, данные, полученные при проведении рекламной кампании в рамках открытых кулинарных конкурсов в г. Николаеве и других кулинарных мероприятий, организованных и проведенных членами Ассоциации кулинаров Украины. Используются различные общенаучные и специальные методы исследования. **Результаты.** С целью анализа эффективности рекламного продвижения гастрономических мероприятий через каналы телевидения, информационные интернет-издания, соцсети осуществлено отслеживание динамики входящего трафика. Анализ осведомленности в регионе о проведении событийного мероприятия указывает, что в современных условиях использование интернет-СМИ имеет положительный эффект. **Выводы и обсуждение.** Существенно отличаются показатели использования таргетированной рекламы в сетях Instagram и Facebook, использованной нами для продвижения мероприятий только в 2019 году, количественные показатели охвата в данных каналах превышают средние показатели просмотров в интернет-СМИ почти на 1000 %. Исследования данных, полученных после мероприятий, позволяют утверждать, что их проведение увеличивает количество посетителей в разы, а иногда оно достигает 250–300 %. Это подтверждает экономическую целесообразность проведения мероприятий.

Ключевые слова: гастрономическое мероприятие, кулинарные конкурсы, продвижение, таргетинг, эффективность, реклама.